

Supporting Information

Tropospheric Aqueous-Phase Oxidation of Isoprene-Derived Dihydroxycarbonyl Compounds

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Sample preparation procedures

Sample aliquots of 2 mL were taken for the GC-MS analysis to identify and quantify carbonyl group-containing oxidation products similar to the procedure reported by Rodigast et al.¹ To these samples, 100 μL of a catalase solution (4 mg mL⁻¹) were added to decompose the excess hydrogen peroxide, thus avoiding possible further oxidation reactions of the formed products prior to analysis. Then, 100 μL of an aqueous solution of 4-(trifluoromethyl)benzaldehyde (6.65×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹) was added as internal standard. Afterwards, 200 μL of an aqueous solution of *O*-(2,3,4,5,6-pentafluorobenzyl)hydroxylamine hydrochloride was added to the sample solution to derivatize the samples for 18 h at ambient temperature. The same procedure was applied for 5 artificial standard solutions to obtain a calibration curve in a concentration range of 1×10^{-6} mol L⁻¹ to 2×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹ for methylglyoxal, glyoxal, glycol aldehyde, hydroxyacetone, acetone, propionaldehyde, acetaldehyde and formaldehyde. Functionalized dicarbonyls were quantified using methylglyoxal as surrogate and its calibration curve to obtain concentrations assuming that the response factor is equal. The pH value of the samples and standards was adjusted to 1 by dropwise adding hydrochloric acid (fuming). The formed oximes of the carbonyl compounds were extracted by adding 250 μL dichloromethane and shaking for 30 minutes. The separated organic phase was analyzed on a gas chromatograph coupled with an electron ionization quadrupole mass spectrometer (GC-MS) (6890A, 5973Network, Agilent Technologies) without any further drying procedure. 1 μL of the sample was injected applying pulsed splitless mode. The parameters and temperature of the chosen method are reported in Rodigast et al.¹

For capillary electrophoresis with ultraviolet light detector (CE-UV) analysis, 5 μL of a catalase solution (4 mg mL^{-1}) was added to 100 μL of the solution taken from the reactor to stop further oxidation, as described above. The analysis was carried out on a capillary electrophoresis system with UV detector (Agilent 7100). The instrument is equipped with an HPCE standard capillary (G1600-62311, 75 μm inner diameter, 72 cm length, Agilent Technologies) operating with a high voltage of 30 kV and 50 μA current. A solution of 5-sulfosalicylic acid ($2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) and tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane ($8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) was used as background electrolyte. The sample was introduced by applying hydrodynamic injection mode (35 mbar for 10 s). For quantification, a 5 point calibration was done for expected product carboxylic acids (pyruvic, lactic, oxalic, acetic, glyoxylic and glycolic acid) to be formed.

A ultra-high performance liquid chromatographic system (UPLC) coupled to a electrospray ionization (ESI) quadrupole/ion-mobility/time-of-flight mass spectrometer (Synapt HDMS, Waters) was used for the identification of possibly formed dimeric products. Samples were injected without further dilution (10 μL). The UPLC system was equipped with an Acquity UPLC HSS T3 column ($2.1 \times 100 \text{ mm}$, 1.8 μm particle size, Waters) at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Acetonitrile (solvent B) and 0.1% formic acid (solvent A) were used as solvents at a flow rate of 500 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ with the following gradient system: 2 minutes 95% solvent A followed by a gradient down to 0% within 10 minutes. 2.5 kV capillary voltage, 25 V sample cone voltage, 2 V extraction cone voltage, 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ desolvation temperature, 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ source temperature and 700 L h^{-1} desolvation gas flow were applied as ESI conditions. Masses were recorded in negative and positive ion mode in the range of 60 – 1000 m/z . As lock spray mass (1S)-(+)-camphor-10-sulfonic acid (m/z $[\text{M-H}]^{-} = 231.0686$; m/z $[\text{M+H}]^{+} = 233.08421$) was used.”

Reagents

The following chemicals were used as purchased, without further purification: NaNO_3 (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.5%), $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (Fluka, 99.0%), H_2O_2 (Th. Geyer, Chemsolute®, 30 wt% in H_2O), 1-oxiranyl-ethanone (Tractus, 95%), methacrolein (Sigma-Aldrich, 95.0%), acetonitrile (Fisher, Optima LC/MS grade), acetic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.8%), sodium bicarbonate (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.0%), ammonium sulfate (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.0%), diethylether (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.7%), magnesium sulfate (Sigma-Aldrich, 97.0%), O-(2,3,4,5,6-pentafluorobenzyl) hydroxylamine hydrochloride (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.0%), 4-(trifluoromethyl)benzaldehyde (Sigma-Aldrich, 98.0%) hydrochloric acid (Merck, 37 wt%), dichloromethane (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.9%).

Synthesis

Synthesis of the DHMP precursor 2-methyl-2-oxiranecarboxaldehyde. In a 500 mL 2-neck-flask, 20.75 g (290 mmol, 1 Eqv.) methacrolein was slowly added to a solution of 37.1 g H₂O₂ solution (30 wt% in ultrapure H₂O (Milli-Q grade, TOC < 10 ppb, resistivity 18.2 MΩ cm), 330 mmol, 3.5 Eqv.) and 5.5 g (70 mmol, 0.2 Eqv.) NaHCO₃. The reaction mixture was heated to 40 °C and the reaction was carried out for 45 min. The product was distilled under reduced pressure and by twice adding 50 mL H₂O. The distillate was saturated with (NH₄)₂SO₄ and extracted with 300 mL diethylether in 6 steps. The organic phases were collected and dried over MgSO₄, and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The product was purified by distillation and 4.2 g (48.8 mmol, 17%) of a colorless oil was obtained. $T_{b(100\text{ mbar})} = 46\text{ °C}$. ¹H-NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ / ppm: 8.87 (s, 1H); 3.11 (d, 1H, J = 4.7 Hz); 3.03 (d, J = 4.7 Hz, 1H); 1.47 (s, 3H).

Synthesis of 2,3-dihydroxy-2-methylpropanal (DHMP). In a 25 mL volumetric flask, 107.6 mg of 2-methyl-2-oxiranecarboxaldehyde (1.25 mmol) were added to 20 mL ultrapure water (Milli-Q grade, TOC < 10 ppb, resistivity 18.2 MΩ cm) and stirred for 96 h at 25 °C to hydrolyse the precursor 2-methyl-2-oxiranecarboxaldehyde. Prior to use, the solution was filled up to 25 mL to reach a concentration of 0.05 mol L⁻¹.

Synthesis of 3,4-dihydroxy-2-butanone (DHBO). In a 100 mL volumetric flask, 430.4 mg of 1-oxiranyl-ethanone (5 mmol) were added to 70 mL of a solution of perchloric acid (0.1 mol L⁻¹) in ultrapure water (Milli-Q grade, TOC < 10 ppb, resistivity 18.2 MΩ cm) to hydrolyse the precursor. The reaction mixture was heated to 50 °C under vigorous stirring for 7 d to hydrolyze

the precursor quantitatively. The solution was neutralized with sodium hydroxide and filled up to 100 mL prior to use to reach a concentration of 0.05 mol L⁻¹.

Table S1. Temperature-Dependent Second Order Rate Constants

Compound	Temperature	OH	NO ₃	SO ₄ ⁻
		k _{2nd} / 10 ⁹ L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	k _{2nd} / 10 ⁶ L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	k _{2nd} / 10 ⁷ L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
DHBO	278	0.8 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.9	1.7 ± 0.1
	288	0.9 ± 0.2	1.7 ± 0.5	2.0 ± 0.2
	298	1.0 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 1.6	2.3 ± 0.2
	308	1.0 ± 0.1	3.8 ± 1.3	2.7 ± 0.2
	318	1.0 ± 0.1	5.6 ± 1.4	3.3 ± 0.3
DHMP	278	1.1 ± 0.1	3.2 ± 1.4	2.6 ± 0.2
	288	1.2 ± 0.2	4.2 ± 1.2	3.0 ± 0.6
	298	1.2 ± 0.1	7.9 ± 0.7	3.3 ± 0.2
	308	1.2 ± 0.2	10.2 ± 0.6	3.7 ± 0.6
	318	1.3 ± 0.1	18.0 ± 6.1	4.7 ± 0.8

Figure S1. Measured and modelled concentration time profiles for the estimation of the OH radical concentration.

Table S2. Initial Concentration of the OH Estimation Model

Species	Initial concentration / mol L ⁻¹
H ₂ O ₂	0.005
OH	0
H ₂ O	55.37
HO ₂	0
O ₂	0
O ₂ ⁻	0
OH ⁻	1.00E-07
H ⁺	1.00E-07
DHBO	0.000121029
products	0

Table S3. Considered Reactions in the OH Estimation Model

Entry	Reaction	Rate constant	Reference
Photolysis	H ₂ O ₂ → OH + OH	2.8 × 10 ⁻⁶ s ⁻¹	Estimated in this model
OH recombination	OH + OH → H ₂ O ₂	3.6 × 10 ⁹ L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	2
OH + H ₂ O ₂	OH + H ₂ O ₂ → H ₂ O + HO ₂	2.7 × 10 ⁷ L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	3
OH + HO ₂	OH + HO ₂ → H ₂ O + O ₂	6.0 × 10 ⁹ L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	2
OH + O ₂ ⁻	OH + O ₂ ⁻ → OH ⁻ + O ₂	1.1 × 10 ¹⁰ L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	4
		k ₁ = 0.0014 s ⁻¹	5
Water equilibrium	H ₂ O ⇌ H ⁺ + OH ⁻	k ₂ = 1.4 × 10 ¹¹ L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	
		k ₁ = 2.3 × 10 ¹¹ s ⁻¹	5
HO ₂ equilibrium	HO ₂ ⇌ O ₂ ⁻ + H ⁺	k ₂ = 5.0 × 10 ¹⁰ L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	
Oxidation DHBO	DHBO + OH → Products	1.0 × 10 ⁹ L mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	This study

Figure S2. Averaged molar yield of hydroxyacetone ($n = 2$) during the oxidation experiments of DHBO as a function of time.

Figure S3. Averaged molar yield of methylglyoxal ($n = 2$) during the oxidation experiments of DHBO as a function of time.

Figure S4. Averaged molar yield of lactic acid ($n = 2$) during the oxidation experiments of DHBO as a function of time.

Figure S5. Obtained percentage turnovers of the OH-driven oxidation experiments of DHBO as a function of time.

Figure S6. HR-ToF mass spectrum of tentative 2,3-hydroxy-2-methylpropanoic acid at an experiment time of 180 minutes.

Figure S7. Averaged molar yield of pyruvic acid ($n = 2$) during the oxidation experiments of DHMP as a function of time.

Figure S8. Obtained percentage turnovers of the OH-driven oxidation experiments of DHMP as a function of time.

Figure S9. Ratio of the molar yields of pyruvic acid to acetic acid during the oxidation experiments of DHBO.

References

1. Rodigast, M.; Mutzel, A.; Schindelka, J.; Herrmann, H. A New Source of Methylglyoxal in the Aqueous Phase. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* **2016**, *16*, 2689-2702.
2. Elliot, A. J.; Buxton, G. V. Temperature Dependence of the Reactions $\text{OH} + \text{O}_2^-$ and $\text{OH} + \text{HO}_2$ in Water up to 200°C . *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.* **1992**, *88*, 2465-2470.
3. Christensen, H.; Sehested, K.; Corfitzen, H. Reactions of Hydroxyl Radicals with Hydrogen Peroxide at Ambient and Elevated Temperatures. *J. Phys. Chem.* **1982**, *86*, 1588-1590.
4. Christensen, H.; Sehested, K.; Bjergbakke, E. Radiolysis of Reactor Water: Reaction of OH Radicals with O_2 . In *Water chemistry of nuclear reactor systems 5*, Thomas Telford Publishing: 1989; pp 1: 141-143.
5. Pastina, B.; LaVerne, J. A. Effect of Molecular Hydrogen on Hydrogen Peroxide in Water Radiolysis. *J. Phys. Chem. A* **2001**, *105*, 9316-9322.